

AREA 1A :
Bursa Uludag University (BUU)
R&I Performance and
Management Capacity
Building

AREA 1B :
Bursa Uludag University
Business Model Innovation
Laboratory (BMI Lab) Set-Up
and Platform

AREA 2

**Research
Programme
(SME Pilots)**

AREA 3

**Long-Term
Impact
Generation**

CAPACITY BUILDING

- Consumer behaviour, marketing and communication (Universidad de Leon (ULE))
- Leadership and entrepreneurship (Atlantic Technological University (ATU))
- Research management and administration skills (ULE, ATU)
- BUU BMI Lab set-up

RESEARCH PROGRAMME

- Turkey hospitality sector analysis
- Organisation and management of SME open calls
- Development of novel business model for 10 SMEs in the hospitality sector
- Impact assessment

SUSTAINABILITY

- Joint strategic research agenda (SRA)
- Joint academic programmes
- Joint EU proposals
- Leveraging on clustering activities
- Engagement of local R&I funding agencies
- Dissemination and communication activities

AREA 1A

Recognised experts from ULE and ATU will provide training to BUU staff through workshops and lectures focused to specific capacities and skills.

AREA 1B

A novel BUU BMI Lab will design, leveraging from the existing Consumer Behaviour Analysis Laboratory at ULE and the ATU DiceLab.

AREA 2

Innovative business models will be developed for SMEs in the hospitality sector in Turkey by using the novel BUU BMI Lab. BMI methodology will be applied to the 3 selected SMEs. After the process is analyzed and the methodologies are optimized, 7 additional SMEs will be selected and the same process will be undertaken. Thus, the impact of BMI effects on SMEs will be evaluated.

AREA 3

SRA will be prepared including joint proposals strategy and preparation, clustering and networking, inventory relevant associations and platforms at EU level, list of events, fairs and congresses to attend, and joint academic programmes preparation. A series of technical workshops and summer schools will be organized to engage students and companies. Emphasis will be made in exchanging good practices among national R&I funding agencies.